

QUIZ

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COURSE CODE : ACA-401

PERIOD NUMBER: QUIZ

INSTRUCTOR: Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ : A COMPREHENSIVE EVALUATION

1. **What are the requirements for writing a successful essay?**

- You cannot write a successful essay unless you give yourself: enough time to read, research, think and write.¹**
- Thesis statement (answer to the question) and an argument.
- I should present and discuss something to develop a thesis.
- Relevant examples, supporting evidence, and information from academic tests or credible sources.

2. **American English has grown steadily in international significance since world war II parallel to which factors?**

- Population
- Magnitude of higher education in America
- International political and economic position of the U.S.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central Africa Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 1.

Growth of the U.S. political, economic, technological and cultural influence worldwide.²

3. **How are the steps of writing process described?**

Publishing, prewriting, revising, editing, writing.

Writing, revising. Editing, prewriting, publishing.

Prewriting, writing, editing, revising, publishing.

Prewriting, writing, revising, editing, publishing.³

4. **What are the prerequisites for writing research papers?**

a) Learn facts and details about a specific subject by reading, observing, and asking question; b) share this information in a clear, organized paper.⁴

a) Credit sources to the original writer or speaker; b) writing the general subject in the centre and then write down all the related topics

that come in mind; C) use a web or cluster to begin your subject research.

a) Begin gathering information.

a) Write basic question about your subject; b) put each question at the top of a separate note card; c) arrange and organize the information.

² Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central Africa Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 27.

³ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, Verne Meyer. *Write Source 2000. A Guide for Writing, Thinking and Learning*, 4th ed. (Wilmington Massachusetts: Great Source Publishing Group, 1999), 5.

⁴ *Ibid.*, 223.

5. **Conceptual questions which are the most common in academic work answer to which question?**

- So what? that helps readers to understand some issue.
- I am working on the topic (x) because I want to find out how, why, whether (y) so that I can help others understand how, why, whether (z).**⁵
- What should I do to change or fix some trouble-some or at least improvable situation?
- What must we understand before we know what to do?

6. **During the research process you face countless specific tasks, but they all aim at just how many goals?**

- Two general goals: ask a question worth answering, and find an answer that you can support with good reason.
- One general goal: draft a report that makes a good case for your answer.
- Five general goals: ask a question worth answering, find an answer that you can support with good reasons, find reliable evidence to support your reasons, draft a report that makes a good case for your answer, revise that draft until readers will think you met the first four goals.** ⁶
- Three general goals: ask a question worth answering, find a reliable evidence to support your reasons, draft a report that makes a good case for your answer.

7. **What does writing research or technical research require in the following?**

- Superlatives and subjective statements to emphasize a point.

⁵Kate L. Turabian. *A Manual for Writers of Research, Papers, Theses, and Dissertations. Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed. (Chicago: university of Chicago Press, 2013), 16.

⁶ Ibid., 18.

- Objectivity.**⁷
- Background.
- Personal beliefs and opinion.

8. **How do you cite and reference books with one author using Harvard Style?**

- Author, date of publication, relevant page.
- Editor, title, date of publication, publisher.
- Translator, date of publication, title, place of publication, publisher.
- Author, (date of publication), title, place of publication: publisher.**⁸

9. **When are colons most often used?**

- To separate items in a series, especially phrases that themselves contain commas.
- To complement or introduce the information in a sentence and a separate emphasis of its own.
- To indicate that an expansion, qualification or explanation is about to follow.**⁹
- To combine two sentences into one without a linking conjunction.

10. **When do collective nouns use plural verbs?**

- When the emphasis is on the whole entity.

⁷ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 4*. 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central Africa Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 7.

⁸ *Ibid.*, 59.

⁹ Tim Cooper, John Jones, Martin Tim, Johnathan Stockwell, Julia Townsend, Peter Workman. *English Style Guide. A Hand Book for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 7th ed. (European Commission: Directorate-General for Translation, 2011), 15.

- When the emphasis is on the individual members.**¹⁰
- When the collective nouns are in plural.
- When a multiple subject clearly forms a whole.

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¹⁰ Tim Cooper, John Jones, Martin Tim, Johnathan Stockwell, Julia Townsend, Peter Workman. *English Style Guide. A Hand Book for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. 7th ed. (European Commission: Directorate-General for Translation, 2011), 32.

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